

Selectively biased tri-terminal vertically-integrated memristor configuration

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Abstract

Memristors, when utilized as electronic components in circuits, can offer opportunities for the implementation of novel reconfigurable electronics. While they have been used in large arrays, studies in ensembles of devices are comparatively limited. Here we propose a vertically stacked memristor configuration with a shared middle electrode. We study the compound resistive states presented by the combined in-series devices and we alter them either by controlling each device separately, or by altering the full configuration, which depends on selective usage of the middle floating electrode. The shared middle electrode enables a rare look into the combined system, which is not normally available in vertically stacked devices. In the course of this study it was found that separate switching of individual devices carries over its effects to the complete device (albeit non-linearly), enabling increased resistive state range, which leads to a larger number of distinguishable states (above SNR variance limits) and hence enhanced device memory. Additionally, by applying a switching stimulus to the external electrodes it is possible to switch both devices simultaneously, making the entire configuration a voltage divider with individual memristive components. Through usage of this type of configuration and by taking advantage of the voltage division, it is possible to surge-protect fragile devices, while it was also found that simultaneous reset of stacked devices is possible, significantly reducing the required reset time in larger arrays.

1 Introduction

Since their conception [1] and eventual fabrication [2] memristive devices have been extensively studied in an effort to incorporate them in circuit designs [3] or in novel neuromorphic computing setups [4]. Increased integration density, which resulted from incorporation in circuits, uncovered issues which impede nominal device operation, such as sneak path currents. A popular mitigation strategy has been the usage of new topologies, such as complementary resistive switching (CRS) [5], 1 selector 1 memristor (1S1M) [6], 1 diode 1 memristor (1D1M) [7] configurations. Other theoretical propositions include using a complementary memristor array composed by two anti-serially connected memristors [8]. At the same time, these technologies also protect from unwanted switching or destructive breakdown of fragile devices, by enforcing a (soft) compliance current through the multiple layers used to fabricate them.

On a separate front, efforts are being directed towards increased range in tuneability of devices [9], especially in settings of neuromorphic computing, where synaptic weight management is of vital importance. By using memristors as standalone components, analogue reconfigurable circuits [10] and threshold logic gates [3] can be fabricated, among other possible circuitry. One commonly

Figure 1: Physical and electrical characteristics of MIMIM devices. (a) graphical depiction of device topology, while (b) electrical equivalent model ('serial' connection). (c) SEM image of the fabricated devices, illustrating the 3 electrodes and their overlap areas which constitute the devices. (d) TEM image of the overlap area, showing the vertical stacking of the fabricated devices. (e) non-switching IVs of a stack, whereby the IV of the total stack is dependent on the IVs of the top and bottom devices, and the resulting voltage division between the two. In this case, two distinct states for the top device were registered and the switching impact on the total stack has been recorded.

40 referenced 'device ensemble' is the memristive fuse [11, 12], which elaborates on the expected
 41 behavior of two memristors in series. Specifically, it has been previously pointed out [13] that
 42 memristive fuse is the natural extension of complementary switching when states in both devices
 43 exhibit analogue behaviour. In all of these 'hardwired ensemble' cases it is not possible to gain
 44 insight into the workings of the separate layers of the ensemble, and fine tuning of states is a critical
 45 issue which has not yet been resolved.

46 Here, we propose a three terminal device, 1M1M topology, which consists of two memristors
 47 fabricated vertically, with an interleaved, but accessible common middle electrode. The case for
 48 three terminal connected devices has already been theoretically made where this configuration is
 49 used to propose neuromorphic or conventional circuits [8, 14]. This configuration allows probing
 50 of the whole stack, while the ability to tune both memristors separately allows fine tuning of
 51 the compound stack's resistive state. Other expectations from this type of configuration include
 52 increased tuneability, simultaneous switching of both devices and an inherent surge protection of
 53 devices due to the stack functioning as a voltage divider, improving resilience. With regards to
 54 fine tuneability, 'super-resolution' memristive ensembles represent an idea that has been explored
 55 theoretically, with cells consisting of two memristors connected in parallel [15], while here we are
 56 implementing it in a serial connection topology. This configuration allows both higher resolution
 57 and higher memory density per unit area. Both are achieved via manipulation of individual devices
 58 with different switching ranges, enabling the set-up of a coarsely-set resistive state originating from
 59 one device plus fine resistive tuning around that state by utilizing the second device. Notably, even
 60 for devices with similar resistive ranges and tuning tolerances, independent control of resistive states

of two devices can achieve better control of the aggregate resistive state. Finally, the superposition of resistive states across both devices, broadens the overall tuning range of the aggregate state, providing further memory density (more available states). For simplicity we shall refer to these effects simply as ‘super-resolution’ in the rest of the paper. Control of forming [16] and/or device manufacture can lead to both ‘serially’ and ‘anti-serially’ connected devices which can exhibit distinct computational behaviours. The difference being that in a ‘serial’ stack, application of voltage of some chosen polarity will elicit the same response from both devices in the stack (both will either increase or decrease resistance).

2 Sample preparation

2.1 Device Fabrication

Device composition consists of two vertically aligned memristors which share one electrode (Middle Electrode - ME) of the stack. To achieve this, five distinct deposition steps were required, one for each layer of the complete device. Patterning of all steps was carried out by negative tone photolithography. A post-lithography surface clean was conducted by using O₂ plasma, through Reactive Ion Etching. Devices were deposited on top of a 200 nm Silicon dioxide (SiO₂) insulating layer, which was thermally grown on top of 6-inch silicon wafer substrates.

In steps 1-3-5 platinum electrodes were deposited by electron beam evaporation, with all electrodes having an average thickness of 12nm. For step 1 an adhesion layer consisting of a thin Titanium film (10nm) was deposited before the deposition of bottom electrodes. Following each metal deposition step a lift-off process was followed by submerging the substrates in N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). Thus, the three distinct electrodes were formed, Bottom Electrode (BE), Middle Electrode (ME) and Top Electrode (TE).

During steps 2 and 4 the active layers for Top and Bottom devices were deposited, for which magnetron sputtering was used. Two different material configurations were explored in this work. In case one, steps 2 and 4 had an active layer (AL) consisting of TiO_x, while in the second case an additional Al₂O₃ was grown on top of the TiO_x in step 2 only. This enabled a first look into combinations of different types of memristive devices. In this case the TiO_x/Al₂O₃ active layer device was selected as it had proven to possess good device characteristics in a previous study [9]. Deposition power used for the TiO_x layer was 2 kW and for the Al₂O₃ layer, 100 W. Flow rates were 8 sccm for O₂ and 35 sccm for Ar gas. A lift-off step was carried out after sputtering.

Final device structure can be summarized as a metal-insulator-metal-insulator-metal (M-I-M-I-M). The two fabricated prototypes were: Pt(BE)/TiO_x(AL1)/Pt(ME)/TiO_x(AL2)/Pt(TE) and Pt(BE)/[TiO_x/Al₂O₃](AL1)/Pt(ME)/TiO_x(AL2)/Pt(TE). Abbreviations in the parentheses denote the function of each layer within the device stack. A complete SEM image of all three electrodes, their access pads and the overlap area can be seen in Fig 1(c), while a visual representation of the cross sectional area is available in Fig 1(a). Finally, 1(b) is a depiction of the electronic circuit which this configuration offers, with each of the three access points depicted as green circles. A TEM image of the cross-sectional area 1(d) depicts the internal composition of the devices ensuring film uniformity and quality.

2.2 Electrical measurements

Memristive devices are initially fabricated as M-I-M capacitors, and they transition into memristors after an electroforming step. This electroforming step is carried out independently for each memristive device in the stack, by making use of the ME. Electroforming and measurements are

104 carried out by using the ArC One platform , previously developed for memristor characterization
105 [17]. This enables the use of highly controllable pulsing schemes for gentle and controllable elec-
106 troforming, as well as controllable and gradual state switching, by utilizing pulse trains instead of
107 IVs. All testing in this work is current-compliance free. The electroforming procedure comprises
108 of 4 repeated steps to ensure successful device activation and has been covered extensively as part
109 of a larger testing procedure in a previous publication [18]. Initially an IV sweep is carried out to
110 ensure good connection to the device and to observe typical rectifying behavior of unformed devices.
111 Afterwards, the electroforming step takes place, in which a pulse train of steadily increasing voltage
112 is sent to the device, until a sharp drop in resistance (to below a specified threshold) triggers the
113 stop condition of the pulsing algorithm (Supplementary Figure S1). A new IV curve of the device
114 is then obtained, which must be pinched, and resistive switching must be observed, for it to be
115 considered as formed. Finally a retention step is carried out to ensure nonvolatile behavior.

116 The forming procedure was applied *individually* for both top and bottom devices. After forming,
117 the possible measurement combinations available are Top device (Td), Bottom device (Bd) and
118 the Complete device (Cd) or ‘Total stack’. Measurements of each configuration were carried out
119 by positioning the probing needles on the TE and ME, ME and BE, or TE and BE electrodes
120 respectively. The third, unused, electrode was not engaged (floating terminal), to avoid any impact
121 on measurement. Fig 1(e) displays non-switching IVs of a fully formed device, with 2 states used
122 on the Top device, impacting the complete device IV, respectively.

123 Here, two types of measurements were carried out. The first type assesses switching impact on
124 the Total stack due to only one device switching. In this case, a resistive readout was taken of the
125 non-switching component and of the total stack, while a pulse train was used to induce switching in
126 the switching component. This was followed by a subsequent resistive readout. For the second type
127 of measurements, concerning the switching of the Total stack, a pulse train was applied across the
128 Top and Bottom electrodes, which could lead to switching in both layers or only one of them. Due
129 to the inherent non-linearity of memristive device IVs and to ensure consistency and comparability
130 between measurements, whenever a resistive state value is quoted, this refers to static resistance
131 under 0.5V read-out voltage unless otherwise specified.

132 3 Characterization

133 Device characterization has been initially carried out by switching one of the two memristors and
134 observing the effect on the Total Stack and then switching the Total stack as a whole and observing
135 the effect this had on the two devices it was composed of. As expected, full-stack resistance changes
136 when either of the devices switches. This can be seen from the non-switching IVs recorded in Fig
137 1(e), where a state change in the top device led to a corresponding state change in the Total
138 stack. However, the total stack operates as a voltage divider and due to: a) the redistribution of
139 voltage within the divider due to generally unequal switching between constituent devices and b)
140 the inherent non-linearity in device IVs, the final resistance of the total stack is dependent on, but
141 not equal to, the sum of resistances of each individual device.

142 3.1 Switching in single layer

143 Individual switching was carried out independently on both of the devices comprising a total stack,
144 as shown in Fig. 2. Figure 2(a,e) indicates which part of the device is switching in each set of
145 measurements. In each case the non-switching device was completely unaffected, as seen in Figures
146 2(b,f), confirming our ability to control devices independently. On the other hand, state switching
147 of a device is transmitted to the full stack, as seen in Figures 2(c,g), when compared with figures

Figure 2: Total stack switching when the bottom device is switched (a-d) and when the top device is switched (e-h). Subfigures (a) and (e) depict the equivalent circuit during programming, where the switching and non-switching components can be distinguished. Subfigures (b), (c), (f) and (g) show the corresponding states of the devices in each step of the experiment, with (b) and (c) corresponding to the Top and Bottom devices of subfigure (a), while (f) and (g) correspond to the respective devices in subfigure (e). Evidence from (b) and (g) shows that the secondary device remains stable, while the switching device is being programmed in (c) and (f) respectively. Subfigures (d) and (h) result from measuring the resistive state of the total stacks ((a) and (e)). In both cases it is evident that total stack resistive states follow the curve set by the switching device, but the relation is not simply additive (in both cases a change of $X\Omega$ in the switching device leads to a change $Y > X\Omega$ at the output).

148 2(d,h) respectively. As a result of this behavior we can achieve high tuneability range of resistive
149 states by finely tuning each one of the two separate devices, which will result in a combined range
150 and potentially increased density/resolution of controllably achievable states in the final stack,
151 increasing state resolution.

152 A convenient way of exploiting this behaviour would be setting the aggregate stack state by using
153 a device with large resistive state range and inter-state gaps for coarse tuning and a corresponding
154 small range/gap device for fine tuning. To illustrate this, we utilize a multistate seeking protocol,
155 which has been described at length in previous publications [9, 19]. In brief, the protocol returns
156 the number of statistically distinguishable resistive states that a target device can achieve. The
157 protocol is applied separately to both the top and bottom devices in the same stack, returning the
158 states illustrated in Figures 3(a) and 3(b). The former depicts short retention runs for all stable
159 states (62) that have been found in the Bottom device, spanning a 2-order-of-magnitude (500k Ω)
160 resistive state window, while the latter shows stable states found in the top device (45), spanning
161 a narrower resistive range (10 k Ω). For this experiment we consider two adjacent resistive states to
162 be distinguishable if they are separated by 1σ deviation.

163 The 3-D map in Figure 3(c) illustrates all states that could be obtained in the full stack,
164 resulting from the sum of states in the two separately tested devices, which can be achieved by
165 separately controlling each individual device. Due to inherent non-linearity and voltage division
166 of devices, the actual resistive values would, understandably, deviate from the calculated values,
167 but the number of states would remain unaltered, as would the expected stack behaviour, due to
168 selection of devices with different resistive ranges. This illustrates the point of a finely controlled
169 super-resolution memristor. In this case, the individual devices have their states spread out in
170 different patterns. The bottom device has a large number of states spread out over a range of 500
171 k Ω , while the top device has all its states within the boundaries of 10 k Ω . This in effect allows
172 for the usage of the top device as a fine tuning mechanism, as can be seen in the rightmost 2-D
173 projection of the 3-D map in Figure 3(c).

174 While many of the states presented here are duplicates, it is obvious that the combination of
175 these two devices results in a state resolution which could not be achieved individually by any of
176 the two devices.

177 3.2 Simultaneous switching

178 This section covers simultaneous switching of devices by using the top and bottom electrodes, TE
179 and BE. This in effect enables the entire stack to work as a single device, but with the added
180 functionality of being able to probe the individual components to ascertain where the switching
181 took place and how it affected them.

182 Two cases are studied in this section, the first is simultaneous switching of serially connected
183 memristors, i.e. with the same switching polarity, while the second case is switching of antiseri-
184 ally connected memristors, i.e, alternate polarity.

185 Figure 4 depicts the first case, where both devices are switched in the same way. Subfigure a)
186 depicts a schematic of the stack and measurement setup, along with an EELS image of the type
187 of device used, which indicates the inner structure of the device from a materials point of view.
188 Switching devices of comparable resistance simultaneously requires sufficient voltage reaching each
189 device. This depends on the allocation of voltage in the potential divider that they form and
190 the relation between the switching thresholds of the constituent devices as explained in [13] The
191 resistive readouts of the total stack are depicted in Fig 4(b).

192 In the first 4 states, as seen in Figures 4(c) and 4(d), the top device exhibits a bigger resistive
193 switch, presumably due to receiving a substantial majority of the divider voltage as indicated by

Figure 3: Improving memory density (number of memory states per device) and resolution per unit area of memristors by exploiting different resistive switching ranges in the top and bottom devices. (a,b) Compiled retention measurements of distinct resistive states in the Bottom (a) and Top (b) devices in the same Total stack, with data obtained by using a measurement routine outlined in previous work [9]. The bottom device has a range of states which spans from single-digit $k\Omega$ to hundreds of $k\Omega$. The top device ranges between approximately 10-30 $k\Omega$. (c) All possible states that *could* be achieved by finely tuning each separate device, calculated by using the sum of possible states of constituent devices. Resistive values shown here will inevitably deviate a small amount from the actual values due to voltage division, but the core concept of increased memory density remains unaffected. Multiple states may overlap (i.e. multiple combinations of top and bottom device resistive states lead to the same total-stack state), but total number of supported states will increase. This is indicative of the devices acting collaboratively in a coarse-fine tuning partnership; As seen in the projection on the right side of the 3D image, the top device would act as a fine tuner for the coarser bottom device states.

Figure 4: Simultaneous switching of memristors with the same switching polarity. Applied voltage is expected to have the same result on both devices, i.e., simultaneous resistive increase or decrease in both devices. (a) Schematic and an EELS image of the stack can be seen. (b) Total stack state evolution, where the first half of the change is driven mainly by the top device while the second half is driven mostly by the bottom device. (c,d) State evolutions for both devices, common x-axis. After the 4th state change, the top device saturates but the bottom device keeps increasing its resistance.

194 the difference in nominal resistances between top device and Bottom device. After the "state 4"
 195 mark, the top device reached a threshold where the voltage applied was no longer enough to switch
 196 it to a higher state. This in turn left the bottom device able to continue its gradual switching
 197 towards higher resistive values, which naturally also led to a higher voltage share being directed to
 198 it. This resulted in the exponential increase in resistive value for the bottom device. Had the top
 199 device not hit a threshold it can be inferred that the switching of the bottom device would have
 200 been severely restricted.

201 Reading or switching devices by using the TE and BE of the stack has the added effect of
 202 doubling as a surge protection mechanism, as the voltage division means that devices will not
 203 receive more voltage than they can process, reducing the probability of device failure.

204 The last part of the test saw the simultaneous reset of both devices by only sending one pulse
 205 through the device. As devices are very sensitive to voltage, especially when applying reset pulses to
 206 them, this approach has multiple benefits. First, due to voltage division-induced negative feedback
 207 the reset pulse is less likely to exceed the absolute maximum device limits, mitigating the risk of
 208 failure. Second, reset time is effectively cut in half. Indeed even if these stacks were to be used
 209 just as two conjoined, but individually operating memory cells, the simultaneous reset could still
 210 prove extremely useful, due to halving memory reset time.

211 Multistate probing in this configuration does not allow full access to all possible constituent
 212 device resistive state configurations, such as when individually switching each component, with an
 213 example of this given in supplementary S2. This comes as a result of the voltage division which
 214 pushes devices to specific states. Thus each time both devices are pushed, the intermediate states
 215 are lost, and in the event of a runaway exponential resistive switching, as depicted in fig (d), the
 216 second device becomes "state-locked", as it will continue to receive a progressively diminished share
 217 of the voltage input, effectively making switching impossible.

Figure 5: Simultaneous switching of antiseriably connected memristors. In this case the voltage applied should have opposite effects on the devices, i.e. it could increase resistance in one and decrease it in the other. (a) Antiseriably connection schematic and EELS image of the stack. In this case the bottom device used was a bilayer stack to ensure cross-fabricational device functionality. Electroforming was used to force T_d to exhibit opposite polarity of switching from B_d . (b) State evolution of the total stack through application of voltage pulses across the aggregate stack. Exceptions to this rule are states 9 and 15, where individual switching was used for the top device, and was carried on to the total stack, in a process already described in figure 2. (c,d) State evolutions of antiseriably connected devices. Evidently from (c), the device state is not affected as much when using lower voltages (+2 or -2 volts), which is what was supplied to the whole stack, leading to the conclusion that higher stimulus would be needed to switch it. For the top device to switch, a pulse of increased voltage (+3 or -3 Volts) had to be separately supplied to it. This led to switching behavior seen in states 9 and 15. During states 9 to 14, whole-stack pulsing is more successful in affecting the whole stack (switching voltage +2 V) and there was a gradual decrease of T_d resistance at the same time as it was increased for B_d . The total device evolution reflects all changes that happen to both devices. For example, transitions into states 9 and 15 are wholly dependent on T_d switching, while states 1-8 and 10-14 closely follow the evolution of B_d .

The second case studied, and depicted in Fig. 5 is for when devices are connected in an antiseriably manner, which could result in contrary behaviour of the two devices for a voltage pulse of any specific polarity. Figure 5(a) presents the schematic for antiseriably connected memristors, accompanied by an EELS image of this stack.

In this specific scenario the stack used was the second prototype, which was fabricated with a configuration of Pt(BE)/[TiO_x/Al₂O₃]/Pt(ME)/TiO_x/Pt(TE), as is evident from the EELS image showing an Al peak in the upper Dielectric/Metal interface of the bottom device. This stack was created to take advantage of increased multistate capabilities offered by the bottom device, and to ascertain if mixing different types of memristors is possible. There were no indications that stacking devices with different active layers might have adverse effects on the switching behaviour of the entire stack. The same fundamental principles governing voltage division and switching conditions hold.

To test this case, a stack was generated, where, after electroforming both devices, one of them would increase its resistance for a specific voltage polarity, while the other would decrease it for that same polarity. The electroforming mechanism responsible for deciding the Set/Reset polarity is outside the scope of this work, nonetheless, it has been found that forming polarity is responsible up to a certain level for switching polarity as confirmed in Supplementary figure S3.

Another important detail is that, for this experiment, the resistive values of the devices are more

236 important than in the previous case. Devices that have similar resistivities might exhibit resistive
237 state changes of the same magnitude, leading to apparent total-stack inactivity, while underneath,
238 both devices are affected. On the other hand, a significant difference in resistance, or switching
239 voltage, will lead to resistive switching in only one of two devices. Here we present the second case,
240 while the "similar resistances and voltage requirements" scenario is presented in supplementary
241 figure S4.

242 Figure 5(b) presents the result of simultaneous switching in antiseriably connected devices. For
243 the initial 8 states recorded, the bottom device followed a gradual increase in resistance while the
244 top device had no reaction to the voltage applied. It is believed that the inertness of the top device
245 is either due to insufficient switching stimulus, a situation exacerbated with the increase in resistive
246 state of the bottom device, or due to it already occupying its current lowest state. Following this
247 initial resistivity increase, the Total stack was reset, by using a pulse of the opposite polarity. Then,
248 the top device was manually switched to a higher resistive state by applying a bespoke pulse train,
249 with opposite polarity from the one used to switch the stack. This led to a resistive switch event,
250 seen in the transition to state 9 of subfigure (c), which also translates to a small state change in
251 subfigure (b). Subsequently, consecutive pulse trains were once again applied to the total stack,
252 which led to a gradual increase of the bottom device, but with a concurrent gradual decrease of
253 resistance in the top device. The resistive change in the top device is not extensive and we believe
254 that the stimulus that now reaches it, due to its higher resistive value, is still not high enough to
255 incite a strong response. Nonetheless, T_d behavior is counter to B_d . This in effect supports the
256 notion that antiseriably connected devices have opposing behaviors, with the whole stack seemingly
257 behaving as theorized by the memristive fuse effect, although it seems more efficient to individually
258 switch the individual devices, considering the apparently fine balance required for meeting the
259 switching conditions of both devices at all times. Next, B_d is once again reset in state 14 (Fig.
260 5(d)), by applying a reset pulse to the total stack, and, afterwards, the top device is also set to
261 a lower resistive state, once again, manually. Finally, another set/reset/set cycle is carried out on
262 the entire stack. The bottom device responds to the stimulus applied, while the top device is once
263 again unresponsive.

264 4 Conclusion

265 A double stack (M-I-M-I-M) memristive configuration was fabricated which combines two devices
266 and the ability to individually switch them by using a middle electrode (ME), or the ability to
267 simultaneously switch them by applying voltage pulses to the top (TE) and bottom (BE) electrodes
268 of the device. Each individual device can be separately tuned, with resulting resistive changes
269 carried over to the full stack. Full stack resistance is dependent on the nonlinearity of individual
270 device IVs and thus is generally not equal to the sum of constituent device resistances, but rather
271 the sum of their static resistances at the voltage shares they receive from the divider. Individually
272 switching the devices and then registering the resistive state of the total stack can lead to increased
273 resistive state resolution and consequently device memory density, even though the intrinsic state
274 resolution of certain device technologies may exceed measurement resolution. Full stack switching
275 can either switch both devices at the same time if they have similar resistivities, or only the most
276 resistive one. Constituent device resistive state will influence the voltage balance in the voltage
277 divider, thus deciding the amount of stimulus they will receive.

278 In the case of serially connected devices of similar resistive range, switching will take place in
279 both devices as long as the stimulus they receive is enough to change their state. For antiseriably
280 connected devices, evidence points towards a "memristive fuse" type of behavior whereby due to

opposing changes in resistive states across the devices, the allocation of voltage in the divider can swing much more widely than for serial devices -in principle-. In the case of similar resistive states (and switching threshold voltages) in antiseriably connected devices, the total stack may function as an attractor with unchanged resistive state, while the individual devices are impacted by the voltage stimulus applied. In either case, the existence of a second memristor in serial connection may, under the right conditions, function as a surge protection mechanism, in the same way as using a resistance in series, protecting each other from catastrophic failure. Finally, in the case of devices with the same polarity, simultaneous reset has been observed, which is a powerful tool to cut reset times in memristor arrays by half.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated *in silico* a 3-terminal component consisting of 2 serially connected, vertically stacked, memristors, which can be used both as a ‘fuse’ and as individual devices. We have shown that: a) the cointegration of the two devices and b) the fact that they share an electrode does not cause any significant deviation from the theoretical behaviours that are expected when examining independent devices, either in isolation or in serial/antiseriably configuration as was done in previous work. Furthermore, we show that it is possible to obtain full-stack switching in these co-integrated devices; the co-integration process does not skew the required switching conditions sufficiently to introduce catastrophic complications. We hope that this work will help the community develop such 3-terminal devices as basic components for applications that can use either their individual or their fuse-configuration properties in the future.

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